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Analysis of Factors Relating to Pregnant Women's Knowledge About Triple Elimination at Andalas Health Center, Padang City

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Abstract

Pregnant mother is group woman vulnerable at risk transmit Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Hepatitis B, and Syphilis to fetus . Effort disconnect transmission of HIV, Syphilis , and Hepatitis B from Mother pregnant to the fetus is one of them with inspection triple elimination . Objective study For know related factors with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas. Study This is study quantitative with analytical and observation methods design cross sectional carried out in the Puskesmas area Andalas . Sample study totaling 98 mothers pregnant taken with method consecutive sampling. Primary data collection uses questionnaire and analyzed with chi square and regression tests logistics. Research result univariate part big own low education , no work , supportive husband , support power poor health , and exposure insufficient information . Analysis bivariate using the chi square test there is significant relationship between education (p-value 0.011), employment (p-value 0.038), support power health (p-value 0.020), exposure information (p-value 0.039) with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination . No there is connection support husband (p-value 0.453) with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination . Analysis Multivariate using regression testing logistics obtained related factors with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination is exposure information and education , the most dominant factors is education (p-value 0.009). Conclusions of educational Research identified as factor related dominant to knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination. Expected Public health centers in Andalas do cooperate cross sector to improve knowledge Mother about triple elimination as an effort promotional and preventive in prevent HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B.

Keywords: Triple elimination, Knowledge , Education

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INTRODUCTION

Pregnant mothers are group woman vulnerable at risk transmit *Human Immunodeficiency Virus* (HIV) and *Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome* (AIDS), Hepatitis B, and Syphilis, where more than 90% of children infected with HIV /AIDS, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B from her mother. As for risks transmission of HIV/AIDS 20%-45%, Syphilis at 69-80%, and hepatitis more from 90%. Transmission takes place in a way vertical from Mother to baby happens moment pregnancy, childbirth, and breastfeeding . This matter indicated that the third disease This own risk of high morbidity and mortality in mothers and children that impact to continuity of life and quality of life child (WHO, 2021b).

world's population of 39 million people is infected with HIV (UNAIDS, 2023), of which 296 million cases of hepatitis B infection, and as many as 7.1 million cases infection syphilis (WHO, 2023). In Southeast Asia in 2021 total HIV infections were 3.7 million cases, Hepatitis infections were 60.5 million cases , and infections of Syphilis as many as 1.4 million case (WHO, 2021b).

Amount target Mother However, as many as 4,887,405 pregnant women were tested for HIV in Indonesia in 2021 only 50.9% did an examination and found 4,466 (0.18%) mothers pregnant women who is HIV positive. Meanwhile, those who do a Hepatitis examination was only 60.3% and 47,550 (1.6%) mothers were found pregnant with Hepatitis B surface antigen HBsAg Reactive. West

Sumatra Province total target Mothers being examined was 114,533 people and 37 (0.8%) mothers pregnant women who were HIV positive. Meanwhile, those who do a Hepatitis examination only 62.15%, and 716 (1.0%) mothers were found pregnant with reactive HBsAg (Kemenkes RI., 2021).

The Ministry of Health in 2017 reflected policy Word Health Organization (WHO) criteria stated in Rules Minister Health No. 52 of 2017 concerning the implementation of triple elimination transmission of HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B from Mother to children carried out at community health centers (Ministry of Health, 2017).

Efforts to disconnect eye chain transmission of HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B from the Mother pregnant to the fetus is one of them with triple elimination examination (Halim, 2019). Triple elimination is a purposeful program To achieve and maintain the elimination of Mother to baby from HIV/AIDS, Hepatitis B, and Syphilis. To reach more health Good for women, children, and their families through approach coordinated. Triple elimination examination is done once during pregnancy at the health center (Sabilla *et al.*, 2020a).

The government set Elimination program targets Transmission of HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B from Mother to children in 2022, with a subtraction amount case infection new HIV in babies born ≤ 50 cases child infected with HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B per 100,000 births life through optimization scope service antennal as well as detection early quality, targeted at 100% mothers pregnant tested for HIV, Syphilis and Hepatitis B in 2022. (Kemenkes, 2017)

METHOD

type of research is Quantitative with *Analytical Observation* research methods using design that is, the researcher carries out analysis or measurement of variables at a certain time or it can be interpreted that the measurement of the independent (free) variable and the dependent (dependent) variable is only carried out once at the same time . This research was conducted at the Andalas Health Center, Padang City. sample using proportional technique done in the region Work Public health center mandalas as many as 7 sub-districts . Variable study consists of variable free (independent) and variable dependent (dependent) Independent variable (dependent variable) is one or more variables whose influence on the dependent variable is deliberately questioned. In this study, the independent variables are education, employment, husband's support, the role of health workers, and exposure to information about *triple* elimination and the *dependent* variable is a variable whose existence or appearance depends on the independent variable. In this research, the dependent variable is knowledge of the *triple* elimination examination.

Primary data with method charging questionnaire To obtain data on knowledge, education, employment, support husband, role Health workers, exposure secondary information and data is the organization's published data. Secondary data collection was carried out by searching or reviewing documents that looked at the results of health examinations obtained by pregnant women from the Padang City Health Department and data from the Public Health Center Andalas in the form of mother's data.

Research instrument The instrument in this research uses a questionnaire, a structured questionnaire is used to measure the variables of knowledge, education, employment, husband's support, role of health workers, and exposure to information.

RESULTS

Analysis bivariate

Connection education with knowledge Mother pregnant about at the Community Health Center Andalas

Education	Knowledge				Total		p-value
	Not enough		Good		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Low	42	42.9	22	22.4	64	65.3	0.011
Tall	13	13.3	21	21.4	34	34.7	

Based on the table on can is known that 42 respondents (42.9%) have an education low to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and as many as 13 respondents (13.3%) have education tall to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained a mark *p-value* of 0.011 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection education of Mother pregnant towards knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination.

Connection work with knowledge with Mother pregnant regarding triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Work	Knowledge				Total		<i>p-value</i>
	Not enough		Good		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
No Work	38	38.8	20	20.4	58	59.2	0.038
Work	17	17.3	23	23.5	40	40.8	

Based on the table on can is known that 38 (38.8%) respondents did not Work own knowledge less, and as many as 17 (17.3%) respondents were working own knowledge Good about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained mark *p-value* of 0.038 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection work the Mother pregnant towards knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination.

Connection support husband with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Support Husband	Knowledge				Total		<i>p-value</i>
	Not enough		Good		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Not enough	6	6.1	2	2.0	8	8.2	0.460
Good	49	50.0	41	41.8	90	91.8	

Based on the table can is known that 6 respondents (6.1%) have support less husband Good knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and 49 respondents (50.0%) had support good husband knowledge about Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination .

Connection support power health with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Support Health workers	Knowledge				Total		<i>p-value</i>
	Not enough		Good		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Not enough	41	41.8	22	22.4	63	64.3	0.020
Good	14	14.3	21	21.4	35	35.7	

Based on the table can is known that 41 respondents (41.8%) have support power poor health to knowledge Mother pregnant menage about *triple* elimination and 14 respondents (14.3%) have support power good health to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* results were obtained mark *p-value* of 0.020 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection between support power health and to knowledge Mother about *triple* elimination.

Connection exposure information with knowledge Mother pregnant about triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Exposure Information	Knowledge				Total		<i>p-value</i>
	Not enough		Good		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Not enough	30	30.6	33	33.7	63	64.3	0.039

Good	25	25.5	10	10.2	35	35.7
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Based on the table on can is known that 30 respondents (30.6%) had exposure insufficient information to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and 25 respondents (25.5%) had exposed good information to knowledge Mother about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained a mark *p-value* of 0.039 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection between exposure information missed knowledge Mother about *triple* elimination.

Analysis Multivariate

Modeling Multivariate analysis Multivariate influencing factors knowledge Mother pregnant regarding triple elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

		<i>p-value</i>	Exp (B)	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Step 3 ^a	Exposure information	0.022	0.338	0.134	0.52
	Education	0.009	3,295	1,343	8,084

At stage third related variables with the knowledge Mothers pregnant about *triple* elimination that is variable exposure information and education. Exposure information has an Exp value (B) 0.338 and education has an Exp value of (B) of 3.295. The most dominant variable is the variable meaningful education higher education own more opportunities Good of 3.295 times for own knowledge better about *triple* elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas, Padang City.

DISCUSSION

Analysis bivariante

Educational Relationship with Knowledge of Pregnant Women about *Triple* Elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Research results can is known that 42 respondents (42.9%) have education low to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and as many as 13 respondents (13.3%) have education tall to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained a mark *p-value* 0.011 (< 0.05) So can concluded that There is a connection education of Mothers pregnant towards knowledge Mothers pregnant about *triple* elimination . In the study This education Mother is Still low The mother does not enough realize about the importance of education because the social and environmental factors around it are less supportive and economic factors can become inhibitor lack of education Which mother got it.

Based on the results of research (Wulandari, 2023), it is concluded that there is a relationship between the level of education and knowledge about *triple* elimination. In line with the research results (Yunida & Syamsulhuda, 2016)) there is connection between education with knowledge of Mother pregnant to examination of *triple* elimination . Research result(Sabilla *et al.*, 2020b) with the title relationship between Age and the Educational level of pregnant women on the Behavior of *triple* elimination examination visits at the Sumberlawang Community Health Center, Sragen. The research results show that there is a connection education Mother pregnant to knowledge Mothers about *triple* elimination

Connection Work with Knowledge of pregnant women about *Triple* Elimination at Community Health Center Andalas

Research results show that 38 (38.8%) respondents did not Work own knowledge less, and as many as 17 (17.3%) respondents were working own knowledge Good about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained mark *p-value* of 0.038 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection work the Mother pregnant towards knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination. In the study This Mother Pregnant many do n't Work because Mother decide For No Work Because want to focus on the pregnancy.

According to Prof. Dr. Soekanto, a leading sociologist, said that work is an activity carried out by individuals regularly and continuously to earn income or meet life's needs. In Soekanto's view, work has an important role in the social structure of society. Apart from that, work can also provide identity and influence a person's social status (Soekanto, 2012). Research result (Sabilla *et al.*,

2020a) also shows majority of Mothers visiting pregnant to Public health center Sumberlawang Sragen's own work as Mother House stairs (45 people or 65%).

The results of the study (Verasita, Budihastuti, and Murti, 2020) show that pregnant women who work outside the home have a logoddd to use triple elimination health services compared to pregnant women who work at home up to 2.23 times the p -value = 0.022). The results of this study state that there is an influence of work on the use of *triple* elimination health. Occupation is the best indicator of a consumer's social class, the work carried out by consumers will influence their lifestyle. Research subjects who work outside the home have broader insight than research subjects who work at home.

Connection Support Husband with Knowledge of Pregnant Women about *Triple* Elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Based on results study obtained 6 respondents (6.1%) supported less husbands Good to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and 49 respondents (50.5%) supported good husbands knowledge of Mothers pregnant about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* test results obtained mark p -value of 0.460 (> 0.05), so can concluded that No There is a connection between supporting the husband towards knowledge Mother is pregnant about *triple* elimination. The results study This support husband Already OK, support most husbands Mother pregnant get it is support instrumental because most respondents answered the question that their husbands provided funds and access to vehicles Where Mother pregnant delivered husband For do *triple* ANC examination elimination.

Study This in line with the study by Istiqhfarin, (2018) which shows that there is no relationship between the husband's support and the counseling and testing behavior of pregnant women. In line with research by Miliyanti, (2018) which states no There is a connection to support between husband to knowledge of Mother pregnant that as many as (68.3%) of respondents received sufficient support from their husbands and as many as (31.7%) of respondents received insufficient support from their husbands.

Connection support power health with knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Based on research results show that 41 respondents (41.8%) have support power poor health to knowledge Mother pregnant menege about *triple* elimination and 14 respondents (14.3%) have support power good health to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination. *Chi-square* results were obtained mark p -value = 0.020 (< 0.05), so can concluded that There is a connection between support power health to knowledge Mother about *triple* elimination. Support power health at the health center Alone Already Good where at the time Mother pregnant do inspection *triple* elimination the examination formula has been given *triple* elimination, still lack support health at the moment Integrated Healthcare Center Mother pregnant Where Still There is posyandu which does not walk whereas exists promotion health about *triple* elimination Can given at the time Integrated Healthcare Center.

In line with research results (Fauziani, Thomson, and Elisa, 2020) show that there is a significant relationship between the support of health workers and the implementation of HIV/AIDS examinations for pregnant women in the work area of the Community Health Center in Rayeuk, East Aceh Regency in 2020 with a p -value = 0.014 < 0.05 . Health workers have an influence on the community in utilizing health services. This influence is in the form of support from health workers which is a driving factor in the use of *triple* elimination examinations. d support from health workers, especially in the form of information support about how HIV, Syphilis, and Hepatitis B are transmitted and their prevention, as well as motivating the community to carry out voluntary *triple elimination examinations*. It is hoped that health workers will increase socialization about the importance of *triple* elimination examinations for pregnant women (Ferdiana et al., 2015)

Connection Exposure Information with Knowledge of Pregnant Women about *Triple* Elimination at the Community Health Center Andalas

Based on research results show that 30 respondents (30.6%) had exposed insufficient information to knowledge Mother pregnant about *triple* elimination and 25 respondents (25.5%) had exposed good information to knowledge Mother about *triple elimination*. *Chi-square* test results

obtained a mark *p-value* of 0.039 (< 0.05) so can concluded that There is a connection between exposure information missed knowledge Mother about *triple* elimination. In study, This papapran information is obtained Mother Still low, mother pregnant only understand about HIV disease but hepatitis B and syphilis Mother Still does not enough know second disease that, lack information obtained Mother result Mother indifferent or does not want to know to disease the.

In line with research conducted (Punguyire et al., 2015)) in Ghana, as many as 81.1% of mothers pregnant in Ghana who have not Been educated about Syphilis, no test for Syphilis , and have connection meaningful with *p-value* < 0.001 Mostly Mothers pregnant exposed information regarding *triple* elimination from the internet, where information from the internet yet Of course true and accurate. The role of the midwife is very important in determining How information This also conveys factor importance in learning somebody. In line study by Musumari, as many as 65.5% of mothers pregnant who acquire information about HIV right, do HIV testing, with *p-value* = 0.008, is present connection between exposure information with HIV testing. The results of this study are in line with(Musumari *et al.*, 2020) that as many as 65.5% of pregnant women who received information about HIV correctly, carried out an HIV test, with *p-value* = 0.008, there was a relationship between exposure to information and HIV testing, giving the correct information regarding HIV and carried out by personnel health, will increase interest somebody For do HIV test. This matter means that exposure to information is also possible to increase the motivation of somebody To do the test .

Study results(Cohn *et al.*, 2021) in sub-Saharan Africa also show that the existence of political policies to support *triple* elimination programs, strategies, funding, and resources that support the implementation of *triple* elimination can increase the coverage of *triple* elimination examinations in pregnant women.

Analysis Multivariate

Variable education has a mark *coefficient* β TThe largest is education, 3.295 with a *p-value* of 0.009 higher education owns more opportunities Good of 3.295 times in know knowledge *triple* elimination. In line with the study (Wulandari, 2023)) the education factor obtained a *p-value* 0.006 (< 0.05), which means There is a connection between education Mother pregnant to importance *triple* check elimination at the Community Health Center. Line research (Wiyayanti and Sutarno, 2023)) shows that higher education carries out more *triple* elimination examinations 38 people (74.5%) compared to basic education amounted to 49 people (43%). So it can be concluded that there is a relationship between pregnant women's education and *triple* elimination examinations at the Wanajaya Cibitung Bekasi Community Health Center.

CONCLUSION

1. Based on the study there is a connection between education, employment, support power health, and exposure to information with pregnant women's knowledge about *triple* elimination in the Andalas Health Center area, Padang City.
2. No there is a connection to support husband with pregnant women's knowledge about *triple* elimination in the Andalas Health Center area, Padang City.
3. The most dominant factor which is related to the knowledge of pregnant women about *triple* elimination in the Andalas Health Center area, Padang City is education Mothers' pregnancies.

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